

Table 1. Reactions of seedlings in seedbox screening for GLH resistance, GLH Collaborative Project.

Variety	Gene	Reactions ^a in						
		Philippines (IRRI)	India (Coimbatore)	Indonesia (Maros)	Malaysia (Bumbong Lima)	Thailand		Vietnam (Hanoi)
						TRRI	EZD	
Pankhari 203	<i>Glh 1</i>	R	S	R	S	MR	MR	R
ASD7	<i>Glh 2</i>	R	MR	R	R	R	R	R
IR8	<i>Glh 3</i>	MR	MR	MR	S	MR	MR	MR
Ptb 8	<i>glh 4</i>	MR	R	MR	R	R	R	R
ASD8	<i>Glh 5</i>	R	MR	R	R	MR	MR	R
TAPL #796	<i>Glh 6</i>	MR	MR	MR	R	R	MR	R
Moddai Karuppan	<i>Glh 7</i>	MR	R	R	R	R	R	MR
IR29 (resistant check)	–	R	R	R	MR	MR	R	R
TN1 (susceptible check)	–	S	S	S	S	S	S	S

^aTRRI = Thai Rice Research Institute, EZD = Entomology and Zoology Division. R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

the thrice-replicated seedbox screening test, varieties were infested with about 5 1st- or 2d-instar nymphs/seedling 7 d after sowing. Damage was rated by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* when 90-100% of susceptible TN1 seedlings died.

In the survival test, three 7-d-old seedlings were transplanted per pot. Each variety was replicated five times with each pot as a replication. Pots were in a randomized complete block design and were covered with mylar film cages. Plants were infested with 10 1st-instar GLH nymphs/cage 23 d after transplanting. Surviving insects were counted 15 d later.

Pankhari 203 (*Glh 1*) was susceptible in India and Malaysia and resistant or moderately resistant at all other locations. IR8 (*Glh 3*) was susceptible in Malaysia and moderately resistant in other locations. The other varieties, except TN1, were resistant or moderately resistant at all locations. ASD7 was resistant in all locations except India, where it was moderately resistant. IR29 was resistant at IRRI, India, Indonesia, Thailand, and Vietnam (Table 1).

Results of the survival study were generally similar to those of the seedbox screening test. ASD8, which was resistant in the seedbox test at IRRI, Indonesia, and Malaysia, and moderately resistant in Thailand, had low nymphal survival at IRRI and in Indonesia and Malaysia, but moderately high survival in Thailand (Table 2). Survival on IR29 was low at IRRI and

Table 2. GLH nymphal survival at different locations, GLH Collaborative Project.

Variety	Resistance gene	Survival ^a (%)		
		Philippines (IRRI)	Indonesia (Maros)	Thailand (TRRI)
Pankhari 203	<i>Glh 1</i>	2 a	0 a	66 bc
ASD7	<i>Glh 2</i>	8 ab	32 b	40 ab
IR8	<i>Glh 3</i>	24 b	42 b	78 cd
Ptb 8	<i>glh 4</i>	76 c	40 b	58 abc
ASD8	<i>Glh 5</i>	14 ab	2 a	72 c
TAPL #796	<i>Glh 6</i>	28 b	32. b	38 ab
Moddai Karuppan	<i>Glh 7</i>	74 c	34 b	32 a
IR29 (resistant check)	–	0 a	0 a	80 cd
TN1 (susceptible check)	–	80 c	74 c	94 d

^aAv of 5 replications. Separation of means in a column by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level; TRRI = Thai Rice Research Institute.

in Indonesia and Malaysia, but high in Thailand.

There was a distinct difference in the reaction of Pankhari 203 to GLH populations in Coimbatore, India, and Bumbong Lima, Malaysia. Pankhari 203 would not be used as a parent to

provide GLH resistance in India and Malaysia. ASD7, however, is resistant everywhere but in India, where it is moderately resistant and nymphal survival is low; therefore, it has good potential as a donor of GLH resistance. *J*

Field evaluation of rices for whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) and leafhopper (LF) resistance

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WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* Horvath has become a serious pest in Haryana. In 1984 kharif, an epidemic of the insect occurred. LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Gn. also is increasing in importance.

We evaluated 43 varieties received

from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project for field resistance to WBPH and LF in 1984 kharif. Two 1-m-long rows of each variety with 10 hills/row and 1 seedling/hill were planted in two replications on 5 Jul. Susceptible TN1 was planted as a skip row after every 10 varieties and around the trial.

To encourage WBPH population, the border rows were sprayed with 0-0.2% methyl parathion at 10-d intervals starting the 1st week of August. WBPH damage was scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*. LF damage

Field reaction of rice varieties to WBPH and LF at Kaul, India.

Variety		WBPH damage ^a (0-9)	LF damage (%)
RP2068-18-35	Swarudhan/Veluthachera	1 ⁺	4
RP2068-17-3-7	-do-	1 ⁺	3
RP2068-18-4-5	-do-	0 ⁺	1
RP2068-18-2-6	-do-	0.5	6
RP2068-16-9-5	-do-	0.5	11
RP2068-18-4-7	-do-	0.5	12
RP2068-18-2-11	-do-	4	9
CO 29	CO 13/CO 14	0.5 ⁺⁺	5
Balamawee	Donor	4	6
TN1	Susceptible check	9	21
T7	Donor	5	4
IET8770	MTU4407/WGL 26888	7	4
IET8769	-do-	7	6
IET8868 (OR405-4)	-	4	9
IET7800	IR20/Shakti	5	9
IET8371	Phalguna/ARC6650	4	11
IET8817 (CR372-48)	-	1	1
RP2199-292-31	Phalguna/TKM 6	6	8
RP2199-84-2	-do-	7	2
RP2199-296-3	-do-	5	11
RP2199-286-26	-do-	5	4
BKNBR1088-83	IR2030-203-3-1/RDI	4	8
T2005	Donor	2	7
Vaizhaeppoo Samba	Donor	2	2
IR4707-106-3-2	IR1888-156/IR2061-213-2	8	5
CO 42	RP31-49-2/Leb Mue Nahng	4	7
RP2071-18-1-1	Swarudhan/NLR9674	4	22
RP2071-22-5-3	-do-	4	11
RP2076-46-4-2	IET6314/NLR9674	4	10
RP2069-3-4-1-2	Swarudhan/Andrewsali	1 ⁺	9
RP2069-3-4-4-6	-do-	1 ⁺	4
RP2069-3-5-2-2	-do-	1 ⁺	5
RP2069-39-3-1-4	-do-	1 ⁺	10
RP2068-12-1-8-1	Swarudhan/Veluthachera	1 ⁺	11
RP2068-15-1-4-2	-do-	1 ⁺	4
RP1579-26	Phalguna/ARC6650	5	3
RP1579-27	-do-	7	12
RP1579-28	-do-	5	9
RP1579-29	-do-	5	10
RP1579-47	-do-	4	8
RP1579-48	-do-	4	24
RP1579-53	-do-	4	11
RP1579-54	-do-	4	33

^a + = did not flower, ++ = late flowering.

Varietal screening for leafhopper and planthopper resistance at Varanasi, India

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We evaluated seedlings of 24 rices commonly grown by farmers in Eastern Uttar Pradesh and those from an upland rice project for resistance to leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* and *N.*

nigropictus, brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens*, and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera*.

Hoppers were reared on TN1. Ten seedlings per variety were grown in each 60- × 40- × 10-cm tray with 5-7 cm of soil. Resistant Ptb 33 and susceptible TN1 and Jelhore were included for comparison. Ten days after sowing, 8-10 2d- and 3d-instar nymphs each of BPH and WBPH and 3-5 leafhopper adults were released on each plant. Each species had three replications in separate trays. The trays were put in an aquarium covered with wire mesh.

Damage was rated by the *Standard*

was rated based on percent leaves damaged per 5 hills. Damage was rated the 3d week of September, when TN1 showed hopperburn.

RP2068-18-3-5, RP2068-17-3-7, RP2068-18-4-5, CO 29, IET8817 (CR372487), Vaizhaeppoo Samba, and RP 2069-344-6 were resistant to both insects (see table). T7, IET8770, RP2199-84-2, and RP1579-26 were resistant to LF. RP2068-18-2-6, RP2068-16-9-5, RP2068-184-7, T2005, RP2069-34-1-2, RP2069-3-5-2-2, RP2069-39-3-1-4, RP2068-12-1-8-1, and RP2068-15-1-4-2 were resistant to WBPH. ☞

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evaluation system for rice when 90% of the TN1 plants died. Five cultivars had resistance to BPH, 11 to WBPH, 9 to *N. virescens*, and 8 to *N. nigropictus*. Only Ptb 33 was highly resistant to BPH (Table 1).

Cultivars with moderate resistance were studied for nymphal survival. Three replications of 1st-instar nymphs of each insect species were placed on 30-d-old plants in pots covered with glass chimneys. Percent nymphal survival, recorded 15 d later, was between 60 and 80% for all varieties but Ptb 33, on which 43-53% of nymphs survived (Table 2). ☞